

Comparative Study of Lithology and Ore Occurrence in Liharmyar Area, Hopong Township and Nawngngwi Area, Kyauktalone Township, Southern Shan State

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Abstract

Liharmyar mine site is located at the north of Hti Chaw Range. It is bounded between latitude $20^{\circ}43'22''$ - $20^{\circ}43'52''$ N and longitude $97^{\circ}13'15''$ - $97^{\circ}14'00''$ E in one inch topographic map no. 93H/2. Nawngngwi mine site is situated about 18 miles south-east of Kyauktalone, the south-east of Inlay Lake, Southern Shan State. It locates between latitude $20^{\circ}18'30''$ - $20^{\circ}30'00''$ N and longitude $97^{\circ}50'00''$ - $97^{\circ}07'20''$ E in one inch topographic map index of 93H/3. Liharmyar area comprises Linwe Formation is overlain unconformably by Plateau Limestone Group and antimony occurred as massive forms. Nawngngwi area composed of Linwe Formation and antimony found as massive, acicular and radiated forms. Antimony observed along fractures and fault zone in the Linwe Formation (Silurian age) of Liharmyar and Nawngngwi areas. Antimony ore mineralization occurs as cavity filling and fracture filling types in sedimentary rocks in both areas. According to X-Ray Map analysis, major elements of Sb from 20.41% to 33.77 % and Si content vary from 61.85 % to 75.41% in Liharmyar area. In Nawngngwi area, Sb content is from 19.03 % to 20.50 % and Si concentrates from 5% to 54.61%. From the X-Ray Fluorescence results, Sb_2O_3 range from 0.814% to 30.8 % and SiO_2 content is from 11.5% to 72 % in Liharmyar area. In Nawngngwi area, Sb_2O_3 vary from 0.311% to 50.6% and SiO_2 ranges from 18.2 % to 69.7 %. In the Liharmyar antimony mine, the ore extracted since 2004. From the total 24379.60 tons of stibnite ore, about 30% sold up in Liharmyar mine. At the present, the Nawngngwi prospect is not been extracted yet.

Introduction

Antimony is a silvery, white, brittle, crystalline solid that exhibits poor conductivity of electricity and heat. It has an atomic number of 51, atomic weight of 122 and a density of 6.697 kg/m^3 at 26°C .

Location and Size

This Liharmyar mine site is located at the north of Hti Chaw Range. It is bounded between latitude $20^{\circ}43'22''$ - $20^{\circ}43'52''$ N and longitude $97^{\circ}13'15''$ - $97^{\circ}14'00''$ E. It falls in one-inch topographic map no. 92-H/2. Detail study of this antimony occurrence, total coverage area is 1.56 square kilometer. Moreover, the comparison of the area, the Nawngngwi antimony prospect is located at the south-east of Inlay Lake, which is situated about 18 miles south-east of Kyauktalone, Southern Shan State. It locates between latitude $20^{\circ}18'30''$ - $20^{\circ}30'00''$ N and longitude $97^{\circ}50'00''$ - $97^{\circ}07'20''$ E in one-inch topographic map index of 93H/3. The location map of the research area and its environs is shown in (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Location map of the research area (Source: UTM map)

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Method of study

The reconnaissance survey of the study area was made in December; 2016. GPS method is used for knowing the location of mineralization. The geological data in the field were plotted on the enlarged map from one-inch topographic map. The representative samples were collected from different rock units. XRF and X-ray Map analyses were done to estimate the percentage of chemical composition and compare the different mineralization observed in the two-research areas.

Purpose of study

The main purposes of research area are as follows:

- to study the distribution of major rock units and to prepare geological map
- to investigate for the ore mineralization in Silurian rock units
- to study the lithology of the Liharmyar and Nawngngwi areas
- to compare antimony ore occurrences in Hopong and Kyauktalone areas

Stratigraphy

The Liharmyar area comprises Linwe Formation (Lower Silurian) is overlain unconformably by the massive carbonate sequence of the Plateau Limestone Group (Permian to Triassic), (Fig. 2, A). Nevertheless, the Nawngngwi area is mainly composed of Linwe Formation, (Fig. 2, B). Antimony mineralization occurs in the Linwe Formation of both in Liharmyar and Nawngngwi areas.

Lithology of the Liharmyar Area

Around the Liharmyar area is composed of Linwe Formation (Mibayataung Group) and Thitsipin Limestone Formation (Plateau Limestone Group).

Linwe Formation (Mibayataung Group)

Linwe Formation is well observed and widely distributed in the western and central parts of the study area, is cropped out at the Hti Chaw Range and east of Nawng hkam village. The lower part of this formation is composed of medium to thick-bedded, light grey, pink and purple colour, phacoidal limestone and whitish grey to ashy grey colour, well jointed, thin to medium bedded shale. The upper part comprises fine-grained, purplish pink colour, thin to medium-bedded, wavy discontinuous silty laminated, unfossiliferous argillaceous limestone (Fig. 3, A) showing phacoidal structure. In some places, minor open folds occur in this limestone. Antimony mineralization occurs as patches within the grey to dark grey colour, sub-phacoidal limestone intercalated with thin-bedded shale. These rocks are striking NNW-SSE direction (340° Azimuth) with rather steep east, dip of 20° to 50°. A minor fold and slickensides are found in the Linwe Formation (Fig. 3, B). The lower boundary of the Linwe Formation is a gradually changed and conformably underlain by Nan-on Formation. It consists of Michelinoceras (Fig. 3, C), and graptolites (Fig. 3, D). This formation is fair fossiliferous in the study area. According to stratigraphic position and fossils content, this formation assigned to Early Silurian in age. On the basis of the lithologic characters, stratigraphic position and fauna evidence, the Linwe Formation can be correlated with Nyaungbaw Formation of Northern Shan State.

Thitsipin Limestone Formation (Plateau Limestone Group)

The Thitsipin Limestone Formation is restrictly cropped out at the north-western part of the study area, especially at the south of Hti-hsaing and north of Naung hkam villages. The most distinctive rock type of this formation consist of thick-bedded to massive, bluish grey to

dark grey colour calcitic limestone (Fig. 4, A). Some chert nodules occur as lenses or parallel to bedding plane within these limestones (Fig. 4, B). Most rocks are massive and calcitic limestone, partly are cherty limestone and locally are dolomitic limestone. Almost everywhere, the unit forms as a network of calcite veins. Some outcrops generally bounded by steep or vertical crags, and have irregular solution holes. The lower boundary of the Thitsipin Limestone Formation is faulted contact with the Linwe Formation. Slickenside appearances occur on the surface of this limestone. The fault scarps also found in the Thitsipin Limestone. The upper boundary of this unit does not observed in the study area. This Formation is fossiliferous but, fossil is a few found in the study area. It consists of a large number of bryozoans (Fig. 4, C), fusulines, brachiopods and coil gastropods (Fig. 4, D). According to the lithology and stratigraphic position, this formation suggested as Middle Permian in age and, it can be correlated with the Tonbo Limestone of Northern Shan State.

Fig. 2 Geological maps show around the (A) Liharmyar and (B) Nawngngwi areas

Lithology of the Nawngngwi Area

Nawngngwi area is mainly composed of Linwe Formation. Linwe Formation is widely distributed in the research area.

Linwe Formation (Mibayataung Group)

The rocks of Linwe Formation well distributed throughout the study area. Probably fault scarp observed on the limestone of Linwe Formation. Sometimes, it is pink to purple in colour due to the enrichment of iron oxide. Calcite vein offset occurs on light grey colour limestone of Linwe Formation, (Fig. 5, A). The Linwe Formation is composed of medium to thick-bedded nature (Fig. 5, C) and light grey to dark colour phacoidal limestone (Fig. 5, B), intercalated with thin-bedded buff colour shale (Fig. 5, D). The strike of the rock is nearly north south (190°) and the dip is generally 48° to 70° . Antimony mineralization occurs as radiated and acicular forms within the grey to dark grey colour sub-phacoidal limestone. In some places, minor folds and slickensides occur in this unit. On the basic of the lithologic characters and stratigraphic position, the Linwe Formation can be correlated with Nyaungbaw Formation of Northern Shan State.

Antimony ore occurrence in Liharmyar area

Liharmyar area is being located at N 20° 42'17'' E 97°12'13'' (Fig. 6, A), at the western foothill of the Hti Chaw range. It is about 30 meter in length and 3 meter in width zone. It is excavating as well as tunneling to the next level and it is now collapse. Mine Site -2 is situated at the N 20°43'31'' - E 97°13'42'', the present antimony production site is about 100 meter in length and 10 meter in width. It extracted by underground mining method, (Fig. 6, B). Mine site -2 has 3 Levels. Each level has 100 feet, (Fig. 6, C). Antimony mineralization occurs as vein-let networks in the limestone intercalated with the shale. Sometimes, the stibnite minerals are acicular forms, which are about 4 cm long, (Fig. 6, D). In some places, stibnite found in the form of pockets and stringer in shape enclosed in the stibnite-bearing quartz vein, (Fig. 6, E). At the mine area, wall rock alterations, such as carbonation, silicification, oxidation and sulphidation observed (Fig. 6, F). Antimony ore content is approximately 20% - 34%. Stibnite bearing quartz vein crossed cut the strike of the host rock of limestone and shale.

Fig. 3 Linwe Formation in Hopong area
 (A) Wavy discontinuous silty laminated argillaceous limestone (Facing 50°)
 (B) Slickenside in the arenaceous limestone units of the Linwe Formation (Facing 290°)
 (C) Michelinoceras in grey colour limestone
 (D) Graptolites in whitish to buff colour shale of Linwe Formation

Fig. 4 Thitsipin Formation in Hopong area
 (A) Minor fault on bluish grey to dark grey calcitic limestone of Thitsipin Formation (Facing 150°)
 (B) Thick bedded, bluish grey limestone with chert layers (Facing 55°)
 (C) Bryozoans in bluish grey limestone unit of the Thitsipin Limestone Formation
 (D) Coil gastropod in bluish grey limestone unit

Fig. 5 Linwe Formation in Kyauktalone area
 (A) Calcite vein offsets on light grey colour limestone of Linwe Formation
 (B) Outcrop nature of phacoidal limestone in Linwe Formation
 (C) Medium to thick-bedded grey colour limestone (Facing 180°)
 (D) Thin-bedded buff colour shale and grey to bluish grey colour of limestone in Linwe Formation (Facing 160°)

Antimony ore occurrence in Nawngngwi area

In Nawngngwi area, Adit-1 is located at N 20°19'07'' E 97°06'05'', (Fig. 7, A). Antimony mineralization confined mostly to limestone of Linwe Formation. Adit-2 is located at N 20°19'13'' E 97°06'07'', (Fig. 7, B). Sulphidation occurred on the ore bearing limestone is slightly folded and are medium to thick-bedded nature, (Fig. 6, D). Sometimes, the stibnite minerals are massive, acicular and radiated forms (Fig. 7, C, E and F). Stibnite needles are ranging from 2-5 cm long. Antimony mineralization formed as the fracture filling and cavity filling types, which are caused by faulting.

Fig. 6 Liharmyar area
 (A) Adit (1), facing 130°, Work site (1), Now collapse
 (B) Open pit mining, facing 20°, Mine site -2
 (C) Tunnel from the main shaft to the Level-2, Mine site -2
 (D) Accicular forms of Main Adit (5), facing 110°, Mine site -2
 (E) Stibnite bearing quartz veins from Adit (3), Mine site -2
 (F) Silicification and oxidation on the antimony ore from Mine site-2

Fig. 7 Nawngngwi area
 (A) Adit (1), Facing 204°
 (B) Adit (2), Facing 290°
 (C) Acicular form stibnite minerals from Adit (1) (Facing 80°)
 (D) Stibnite bearing sulphidation zone from Adit (2) (facing 120°)
 (E) Acicular form stibnite minerals from Adit (1) (Facing 80°)
 (F) Radiated forms of stibnite minerals Acicular form stibnite minerals from Adit (1) (Facing 80°)

Physical Properties of Antimony

Chemical Composition	Sulphide Stibnite(Sb₂S₃)
Color	Tin-white
Crystal System	Trigonal
Streak	Tin white to gray
Form	Commonly massive, radiated, acicular
Luster	metallic
Fracture	Uneven
Tenacity& Diaphaneity	Brittle, opaque
Moh's Hardness	3-4
Specific Gravity	6.6-6.7
Occurrence	In hydrothermal Sb–Ag veins

Geochemical Analysis of Antimony

According to the XRF data in (Table. 1), stibnite content in comparative study of two areas exhibit in the following. In Liharmyar area, the concentration of Sb₂O₃ range from 0.814% to 30.8 % and SiO₂ content is from 11.5% to 72 %. Moreover, stibnite is associated with minor amount of Pb, Zn, Ti and Fe. In Nawngngwi area, Sb₂O₃ contents vary from 0.311% to 50.6% and SiO₂ concentration range from 18.2 % to 69.7 %. Furthermore, stibnite is associated with minor amount of Pb, Ti, Rb and As. According to X-Ray Map analysis in (Table. 2), antimony from Liharmyar area indicates that the major elements contained in antimony are Sb content is from 20.41% to 33.77 % and Si content vary from 61.85 % to 75.41% with minor amount of Ca, Na, Mg, Fe, S, Al, K and Si. Antimony from Nawngngwi area indicates that the concentration of Sb content is from 19.03 % to 20.50 % and Si concentrates from 5% to 54.61% together with the same minor elements of Liharmyar area.

Table.1 The content of major element (wt %) in antimony ore bearing samples from Liharmyar and Nawngngwi areas, analysed by XRF method. ND= Not Detected

Area	Liharmyar				Nawngngwi		
Location	20°43'32''N 97°13'50''E				20°19'07''N 97°06'05''E		
Sample No	L-1	L-2	L-3	L-4	N-1	N-2	N-3
SiO₂	11.5	34.9	41.9	72	69.7	67.8	18.2
Al₂O₃	4.5	3.65	1.02	15.5	18.8	18.9	4.65
CaO	78.3	6.79	ND	0.47	0.169	ND	ND
Fe₂O₃	2.18	0.269	0.362	4.95	3.16	3.9	1.03
K₂O	1.09	0.645	0.191	4.27	5.67	6.21	1.07
SO₃	0.343	23.6	25.4	0.115	0.064	0.21	23.2
Sb₂O₃	0.814	29.3	30.8	0.998	0.311	0.505	50.6
As₂O₃	ND	ND	0.245	0.01	0.01	0.007	ND
ZnO	ND	0.012	0.013	0.009	ND	ND	ND
CuO	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
PbO	ND	0.099	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.156
TiO₂	ND	0.099	ND	0.525	0.786	0.719	0.224
Rb₂O	ND	ND	ND	0.011	0.018	0.018	ND

Table.2 X-Ray Map analysis, the major elements contained in antimony from Liharmyar and Nawngngwi areas, ND= Not Detected

Area	Liharmyar			Nawngngwi	
Location	20°43'32"N 97°13'50"E			20°19'07"N 97°06'05"E	
Sample No	0-1	0-2		0-4	0-6
Al	0.33	0.96	0.38	4.87	0.98
Si	64.38	61.85	75.41	54.61	5.00
K	0.75	ND	0.41	1.95	0.11
Cr	0.00	ND	ND	ND	ND
Fe	0.54	0.88	2.85	3.58	1.79
Sb	33.77	23.04	20.41	20.50	19.03
Ce	0.00	0.24	ND	ND	ND
Pb	0.22	0.36	0.48	0.24	0.02
S	ND	12.69	ND	13.42	7.17
V	ND	ND	0.05	ND	ND
Ni	ND	ND	0.02	ND	ND

Conclusion and Discussion

Liharmyar area occurs as cavity filling and fracture filling types in sedimentary rocks. Most antimony deposits formed by hydrothermal solution at low temperature and shallow depth, giving rise to filled fissures, joints, to irregular replacement deposits and are found as massive forms. Mineralization is frequently found as vein-lets and pockets. In Nawngngwi area, antimony mineralization confined mostly to limestone of Linwe Formation. The ore bearing limestone slightly folded and antimony minerals found as massive, acicular and radiated forms. In the research area, the ore bearing fluids may have migrated through the porous limestones and deposited in favorable fissure-type solution channels. Thus, antimony mineralization was post-dolomitization, which gave rise to a higher porosity and permeability in the carbonate rocks that supports the evidence for epigenetic character. The mineralization occurred along the fractures of limestone. Therefore, the ore deposits are stratabound. Antimony-bearing ore veins occurred in brecciated rocks, mostly observed in the limestone of Linwe Formation. As no igneous rocks occur in the study area, the mineralization cannot be attributed mainly magmatic ore forming processes. The ore deposits are controlled by structure and lithology in the localized and regionalized of the research area. The antimony of research area are carbonate-hosted, stratabound deposits and epigenetic in origin. In this research, the researcher used antimony as semiconductor technology for making infrared detectors, diodes, hall-effect devices, alloys, batteries, tracer bullets, LED touch, smartphone touch, cable sheathing, cosmetic and medicine.

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